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Effect Of Financial Liberalization On Stability Of Nigeria Economy

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the effect of financial liberalization on stability of Nigeria economy. The specific objectives are to evaluate the: effect of interest rate on the stability of Nigeria economy, effect of market capitalization on the stability of Nigeria economy, effect of credit to private sector on the stability of Nigeria economy between the periods Of 1985-2024. Ordinary Least Squared (OLS) method of data analysis was used. Secondary sources of data were employed, the interested variables were culled from the central bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin 2024. The following variables were used, interest rate, credit to private sector, market capitalization and real gross domestic product. The value of R-squared which is the co-efficient of the determination stood at 0.92% which stood that 92% of the systematic variations in individual dependent variables were explained in the model while about 8% were unexplained. The findings showed, interest rate have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy, market capitalization does not have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy, Credit to private sector have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy. The researcher recommends that The Central Bank of Nigeria should implement policies towards the reduction of interest rate in the country, in that it has a negative relationship with economic growth. Since, as interest rate increases economic growth decreases, interest rate should be controlled to its minimum. The Government of Nigeria should develop policies which are geared toward the supply of more money into the economy, in that result has shown that more money in the economy increases the growth of the economy. This can be done through embarking on capital projects, provision of social infrastructural facilities and so on.

Keywords: financial liberalization, stability, interest rate, credit to private sector, market capitalization and real gross domestic product

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Financial liberalization refers to the deregulation of financial markets, aimed at reducing government controls and restrictions on financial institutions and markets. It encompasses policy reforms such as the removal of interest rate ceilings, elimination of credit controls, reduction of entry barriers for banks and financial institutions, and liberalization of the foreign exchange market (Folarin, 2019). These reforms are designed to enhance efficiency in the financial sector by encouraging competition, improving resource allocation, and attracting domestic and foreign investment (Adesegun, 2014),.

In the context of developing economies like Nigeria, financial liberalization emerged in the late 1980s as part of structural adjustment programs (SAP) promoted by international financial institutions, including the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF). Prior to these reforms, Nigeria's financial system was characterized by stringent regulations, fixed interest rates, and restricted entry into the banking sector (Agbaeze, & Onwuka, 2014).. Such regulations were intended to support government-

directed credit programs but often resulted in inefficiencies, credit misallocations, and inhibited the growth of a robust financial sector. In 1986, Nigeria formally adopted financial sector reforms as part of its SAP to liberalize interest rates, deregulate credit allocation, and allow market forces greater influence over financial intermediation (Fasanya, & Olayemi, 2020). Subsequent policies, including the Bankers' Deregulation Policy and reforms in foreign exchange controls, were aimed at fostering competition, mobilizing savings, and encouraging investment. These measures were expected to stimulate economic growth and enhance macroeconomic stability by creating a more resilient and efficient financial system (Agu, Orji, & Egbiremolen, 2014).

However, the outcomes of financial liberalization in Nigeria have been mixed. While some reforms have contributed to increased financial depth and expanded financial services, critics argue that liberalization has also exposed the financial system to volatility, bank failures, and heightened systemic risks (Akinsola, Foluso Odhiambo, & Nicholas 2017). Issues such as weak regulatory frameworks, corporate governance challenges, and inadequate risk management practices have, at times, undermined the intended benefits of liberalization. Episodes of financial instability, such as the banking sector crisis of the late 1990s and early 2000s, underscored the vulnerabilities within the financial system despite liberalization efforts (Egbetunde, Ayinde, & Balogun, 2017). Given Nigeria's central role in sub-Saharan Africa's economy and its significant reliance on financial intermediation for growth and development, understanding the relationship between financial liberalization and economic stability remains a critical policy concern. Researchers and policymakers continue to debate whether the benefits of financial liberalization such as improved efficiency, greater investment, and enhanced access to financial services outweigh the potential risks related to financial instability, economic shocks, and systemic fragility. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the impact of financial liberalization on the stability of the Nigerian economy.

Financial liberalization was introduced in Nigeria with the expectation that deregulating the financial sector would enhance efficiency, promote investment, deepen financial markets, and ultimately foster economic stability. Since the adoption of liberalization policies under the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986, Nigeria has implemented various reforms including interest rate deregulation, exchange rate liberalization, banking sector reforms, and the removal of credit controls. Despite these reforms, the Nigerian economy has continued to experience recurrent episodes of macroeconomic instability manifested in inflationary pressures, exchange rate volatility, banking sector distress, and fluctuating economic growth.

Although financial liberalization is theoretically expected to strengthen economic stability through improved financial intermediation and efficient allocation of resources, Nigeria's experience suggests that these outcomes are not automatic. The liberalized financial environment has at times been associated with excessive risk-taking by financial institutions, weak regulatory oversight, capital flight, and vulnerability to external shocks. The banking crises witnessed in the late 1990s and the global financial crisis of 2008 further raised concerns about the capacity of Nigeria's financial system to withstand instability under a liberalized framework.

Empirical studies on financial liberalization and economic stability in Nigeria have produced mixed and sometimes contradictory findings. While some studies argue that liberalization has enhanced financial deepening and growth, others contend that it has exacerbated economic volatility and weakened macroeconomic stability. Moreover, many existing studies focus predominantly on economic growth, neglecting broader indicators of economic stability such as inflation, exchange rate fluctuations, financial sector soundness, and output volatility.

This lack of consensus in the literature creates a gap in understanding the true impact of financial liberalization on the stability of the Nigerian economy. Consequently, policymakers continue to face challenges in designing financial reforms that balance market efficiency with financial stability. Addressing this gap is crucial, given Nigeria's aspiration for sustainable economic development and resilience in an increasingly globalized financial system. This study therefore seeks to examine the effect of financial liberalization on the stability of the Nigerian economy, with a view to providing empirical evidence that can guide effective policy formulation and implementation.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to examine effect of financial liberalization on the stability of Nigeria economy: the Nigerian experience. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the effect of interest rate on the stability of Nigeria economy
2. Ascertain the effect of market capitalization on the stability of Nigeria economy.
3. Examine the effect of credit to private sector on the stability of Nigeria economy

1.3 Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated that guide the objectives of the study and strengthen the analysis:

Ho₁: Interest rate has no significant effect on the stability of Nigeria economy

Ho₂: Market capitalization has no significant effect on the stability of Nigeria economy

Ho₃: Credits to private sector has no significant effect on the stability of Nigeria economy

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Financial liberalization

According to Kaminsky and Schmukler (2013). Financial liberalization consists of the deregulation of the foreign sector capital account, the domestic financial sector, and the stock market sector viewed separately from the domestic financial sector. The financial system performs a number of important functions in an economy. Basically, it takes care of mobilizing financial resources, facilitating risk management, allocating resources to the most efficient projects, monitoring the use of financial resources (exerting corporate governance), and providing a payment system that makes trade among economic participants more efficient(Levine, 2017). Financial development occurs when a financial system is able to improve on performing these functions. There is a large body of theoretical and empirical work emphasizing that financial development is positively associated with economic growth. Closely related to the discussion of the relationship between finance and growth is the discussion of the role that financial liberalization can play in this relationship. The main idea is that financial liberalization may impact on financial development which, in turn, affects economic growth.

Financial liberalization can be viewed as a set of operational reforms and policy measures designed to deregulate and transform the financial system and its structure with a view to achieve a liberalized market- oriented system within an appropriate regulatory framework (Johnston and Sundararan, 2019). Financial liberalization has been variously characterized in the empirical literature but Niels and Robert (2015) observed that whatever characterization, financial liberalization usually include official government policies that focus on deregulating credit controls, deregulating interest rate controls, removing entry barriers for foreign financial institutions, privatizing financial institutions, and removing restrictions on foreign financial transactions. In other words, financial liberalization has both domestic and foreign dimension. Moreover, it focuses on introducing or strengthening the price mechanism in the market, as well as improving the conditions for market competition.

2.1.2. Stability

Stability refers to the condition in which a system, structure, or process maintains consistency, balance, and continuity over time, while effectively absorbing internal and external shocks without experiencing significant disruption or collapse. It implies a state of relative equilibrium, where fluctuations occur within manageable limits and do not threaten the system's core functions or long-term sustainability. In a broader sense, stability denotes the capacity of an entity economic, social, political, or institutional to withstand disturbances, adapt to changing conditions, and return to a desirable or functional state after periods of stress or uncertainty. Stability does not necessarily imply the absence of change; rather, it emphasizes orderly and predictable change that supports sustained performance and development.

In economics, stability refers to the ability of an economy to maintain steady growth, controlled inflation, sustainable employment levels, and a sound financial system, despite exposure to shocks such as policy changes, global financial crises, capital flow volatility, or commodity price fluctuations. An economically

stable system minimizes extreme cycles of boom and recession, ensuring that economic variables adjust smoothly rather than violently.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the Financial Liberalization Theory. The liberalization of the capital account is captured by the regulations on offshore borrowing by financial institutions and by non-financial corporations, on multiple exchange rate markets and on capital outflow controls. In a fully liberalized capital account regime, banks and corporations are allowed to borrow abroad freely. They may need to inform the authorities but permission is granted almost automatically. Reserve requirements might be in place but are lower than 10 per cent. In addition, there are no special exchange rates for either the current account or the capital account transactions; nor are there any restrictions to capital outflows. A fully liberalized domestic financial system is characterized by lack of controls on Lending and borrowing interest rates and certainly, by the lack of credit controls, that is, no Subsidies to certain sectors or certain credit allocations. Also, deposits in foreign currencies are permitted. In a fully liberalized stock market, foreign investors are allowed to hold domestic equity without restrictions and capital, dividends and interest can be repatriated freely within two years of the initial investment.

According to Kaminsky and Schmukler (2003), financial liberalization theory, then, argues for improved economic growth through financial sector reforms. The supporters of financial liberalization base their arguments on the works of McKinnon and Shaw. According to the theory, positive real deposit rates raise the saving rate, thus increasing the flow of financial savings. Developing countries with repressed financial systems thus mounted financial reforms aiming at: mobilization of financial resources with increased amounts of domestic savings channeled through the formal financial sector, reducing the role of direct controls in determining the allocation of credit, increasing reliance on market based system of monetary control and broadening the range of domestic sources of finance.

2.3. Empirical Review

Ngangah, Egungwu, & Nduka, (2025). assessed the effects of financial liberalization on Nigeria's economic development from 1986 to 2022. The research analyzed variables such as Lending Rate (LIR), Exchange Rate (EXR), Capital Account Openness (KAOPEN), Market Capitalization (MCP), and Private Sector Credit (PSC) as independent variables, with the Human Development Index (HDI) representing economic development. Using data from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and World Bank Development Indicators, the study employed econometric techniques including Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests, ARDL Bound Tests, Error Correction Mechanism (ECM), and ARDL model estimation for analysis. Findings revealed financial liberalization positively and significantly impacted HDI ($C = 12.42928$, $P = 0.000001$). LIR, KAOPEN, and PSC demonstrated significant positive effects on HDI, while EXR and MCP had mixed, insignificant impacts.

Ozuzu, Reginald, Nwankwo, & Odungweru (2024).examined the relationship between financial sector liberalization and Nigeria economic growth. Time series data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin from 1990- 2023. Financial sector liberalization were proxy by savings rate liberalization, lending rate liberalization, exchange rate liberalization, capital market liberalization and current account liberalization while Nigeria economic growth was proxied by real gross domestic product. Multiple regressions with econometrics view statistical package were used as data analysis techniques. Co-integration, Granger Causality Test and Augmented Unit Root Test were used to determine the long and the short run relationship that exist among the variables. Findings of the study revealed that current account liberalization, capital market liberalization and lending rate liberalization have negative relationship with Nigeria economic growth while exchange rate liberalization, and savings rate liberalization have positive relationship with Nigeria economic growth.

Oji, (2025) examined financial deepening and Nigerian economic growth. The main purpose is to examine the relationship between financial deepening and Nigerian economic growth while the specific objectives are to examine the impact of interest rate, capital market development, rational savings, credit to private sector and broad money supply on the growth of Nigerian. Secondary data of the variables were

sourced from the publications of Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) from 1990-2023. Nigerian Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) was used as dependent variable while Broad money supply (M2), Credit to Private Sector (CPS), National Savings (NS), Capital Market Capitalization (CAMP) and Interest Rate (INTR) was used as independent variables. Multiple regressions with E-view statistical package were used as data analysis techniques. Cointegration test, Augmented Dickey Fuller Unit Root Test, Granger causality test was used to determine the relationship between the variable in the long-run and short-run. R^2 , F – statistics and β Coefficients were used to determine the extent to which the independent variable affects the dependent variable. It was found from the regression result that Broad Money Supply, credit to private sector have position effect on the growth of Nigerian Real Gross Domestic Product while National Savings, Capitalization and Interest Rate on Nigeria Real Gross Domestic Product. The co-integration test revealed presence of long-run relationship among the variables, the stationary test indicated stationarity of the variables at level. The Granger Causality Test found bi – variant relationship from the dependent to the independent and from the independent to the dependent variables. The regression summary found 99.0% explained variation, 560.5031, F – statistics and probability of 0.00000. From the above, the study concludes that financial deepening has significant relationships with Nigerian economic growth.

Chinonso Uzoamaka, & Akujuobi, (2023) examine the effectiveness of financial liberalization in economic growth of Nigeria from 1970 to 2020. The required data for the study were sourced from various sources including Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and Annual Reports, and the World Bank Development Indicators among others. To eliminate the problem of spurious regression in the study, the technique of Phillips-Perron unit root test was employed. In addition, the long-run equilibrium relationship in the exogenous series was tested with the ARDL Bounds Test. More so, the Diagnostics tests of Jarque-Bera, Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM and Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey were also employed to test normal distribution, autocorrelation and Heteroskedasticity in the data, while Wilcoxon Test Statistic investigated the change in the pre and post deregulation periods. The findings revealed that official exchange rate and one period lag of real interest rate are positively and significantly related to the economic growth, while real interest rate without lag has negative and significant relationship on the economic growth of Nigeria. It was further revealed that credit to private sector and inflation rate have negative coefficients. Lastly, the study showed a significant change in gross domestic product per capita and official exchange rate in the pre- and post-liberalization periods.

Nwakwe, Echekoba, and Ezu, (2025) examined the effect of financial liberalization on economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, the effect of credit to private sector, real exchange rate, trade openness, interest rate deregulation, and commercial banks credit to deposit ratio on real gross domestic product were determined. The study covered a time frame of thirty seven (37) years that is, from 1986 to 2022 based on available data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin of 2022. The study employed an “ex-post facto” research design with the aid of the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and granger causality techniques to analyse the data and anchored on the Mckinnon and Shaw Complimentary Hypothesis. The result of Granger Causality test revealed that credit to private sector (p-value $0.1719 > 0.05$), real exchange rate (p-value $0.2273 > 0.05$), trade openness (p-value $0.7026 > 0.05$), interest rate deregulation ($0.2001 > 0.05$) and commercial banks credit to deposit ratio (p-value $0.8595 > 0.05$) have no significant effect on real gross domestic product as a measure of economic growth in Nigeria. Similarly, credit to private sector (p-value $0.1281 > 0.05$), trade openness (p-value $0.0675 > 0.05$), and commercial banks credit to deposit ratio (p-value $0.6615 > 0.05$) have negative insignificant positive relationship with real gross domestic product respectively; real exchange rate has significant negative relationship with real gross domestic product (p-value $0.0067 < 0.05$); while interest rate has insignificant negative relationship with real gross domestic product (p-value $0.9211 > 0.05$).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Methodology is a set of rules and procedures upon which research is based and against which claims for knowledge and assumptions are evaluated for decision making. It can also be said to be the specification for collecting and analysing the data necessary to help solve the problem the country obtaining various

levels of accuracy is minimized. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) techniques shall be employed in obtaining the numerical estimates of the co-efficient in different equation. The OLS method is chosen because it possesses some optimal properties, its computation procedures is fairly simple and it is also an essential component of most order estimation techniques. The estimation period covers the period 1985 to 2024. In demonstrating the application of ordinary least square method the multiplier linear regression analysis will be used with real gross domestic product as the dependent variables while financial development as the explanatory variables.

3.1 Model Specification

This research shall employ econometric method according to Gujarati, D. (2004), this method gives the best techniques for the verification and reputation of theories it also provides quantitative estimation of the relationship among variables without much subjective judgment. The specification of econometrics model is always based on econometrics theory or any available information relating to the phenomenon being studied (Koustsoyiannis 1997), hence the specification of the model adopted for this investigation is implicitly stated as follows

$$RGDP = F (INT, MCAP, CPS)$$

WHERE

RGDP = Real gross domestic product (proxy of Stability)

INT, = Interest rate

MCAP =Market capitalization

CPS = Credit to private sector

F=functional notation

The econometric form of the model can be expressed as;

$$RGDP = B_0 + B_1DINV + B_2INT + CPS + \mu$$

Where; B_0 is the constant intercept

B_1 =coefficient of parameter DINV

B_2 = coefficient of parameter INT

B_3 = coefficient of parameter CPS

μ = the stochastic error term or disturbance variable.

The model can be re-write in an logged form

$$LRGDP=C + Lb_1 DINV + b_2INT + Lb_3 CPS+\mu$$

Where

Log=logged values of the variables

3.2 Evaluation Techniques

An evaluation of the model enables the researcher to determine where the estimated coefficients are theoretically meaningful and statistically satisfactory. The variables in this work will be tested with the economic test, first order statistical test and second order econometric test.

Error Correction Mechanism (ECM).

The ECM approach helps to solve the spurious correlation problem among economic variables. Therefore, a co-integration model captures the three relationship economists is interested in the short run effect of the explanatory variables on the dependent variables, their equilibrium effect and the error correlation mechanism of the current level of the dependent variables towards its equilibrium level (Nkuzuziza, 2002).

3.3 Data Sources

Data for the survey were sourced from the secondary methods. The secondary sources of data or information are with respect to existing literature, research reports, and government documents etc. These secondary sources of data for this study were sought through the following sources, including Central Bank of Nigeria(CBN) statistical Bulletin, various years, Time series and Economic and financial. The variables uses were on stability, interest rate, market capitalization from the period of 1985-2024.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter presents the empirical results and discussion of findings, ordinary least square was used as techniques for the analysis, the result was subjected to different statistical and econometrics test. We begin by discussing the order of integration of the interest variables.

4.1 Unit Root Test

The first stage of co-integration and Error Correction Model is to test for unit root, the whole analysis then proceed from it. Konya (2004) maintains that there exists unit root in most macroeconomics time series data. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze whether the series are stationary or not whenever time series data are involved. The presence of unit root implies that the time series under investigation is non-stationary, the absence of a unit roots shows that stochastic process is stationary. The augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test would be employed in this test

Tables 4.1 Unit Root Result

Variable	ADF	Integration	Significance
RGDP	-10.01860	I (1)	1%
INT	-4.581561	I (2)	1%
MC	-4.697873	1 (1)	1%
CPS	-4.069581	I (1)	1%

Source: Author’s computation using e-view version 10

Following the result of ADF test above it is observed that none of the variables are stationary at level, however, real gross domestic product, market capitalization and credit to private sector were integrated at 1st difference, while interest rate is integrated at 2nd difference. This simply show that all the included variables were stationary and this give way to co-integration test.

4.2 Co-integration analysis

The aim of co-integration analysis is to determine the long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables. Co-integration exists among the variables if they are integrated of the same order. The implication of this analysis is that deviation or drift may occur between the variables but this is temporary as equilibrium hold in the long run for them. In this study we used the Johansen co integration approach to examine the existence of long-run relationship between the variables of interest. Below is the summary of co integration results

Table 4.2 co-integration result test

Unrestricted Co-Integration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace static	0.05 critical value	Prob**
None *	0.615725	75.40486	54.07904	0.0002
At most 1*	0.483628	40.01817	35.19275	0.0140
At most 2*	0.237121	15.56386	20.26184	0.1958
At most 3*	0.139283	5.549604	9.164546	0.2285

Source: Author’s computation using e-view version 10

Trace test indicates 2 co-integrating equ(s) as the 0.05 level* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level ** mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) P – value

Unrestricted co-integration Rank Test (Maximum Eigen value)

Hypothesized CE(s)	No of	Eigen value	Trace static	0.05 critical value	Prob
None *		0.615725	35.38669	28.58808	0.0058
At most 1*		0.483628	24.45431	22.29962	0.0246
At most 2*		0.237121	10.01426	15.89210	0.3331
At most 3*		0.139283	5.549604	9.164546	0.2285

Source: Author's computation using e-view version 10

Max-Eigen value test indicates 2 co-integrating equ(s) at the 0.5 level* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level **mackinnon-Haug-michelis (1999) P-values. Max-Eigen value and trace test indicates 2 co-integrating equations respectively at the 0.05 level. This suggests a long run equilibrium relationship among the variables. Co-integration is a pre-requisite for error correction mechanism following the result of co-integration, there is a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables, hence, we can move over to error correction mechanism.

4.3 Presentation of Regression Result

Table 4..3 Error Correction Model Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	T-statistics	Prob
C	0.904410	0.835526	1.082445	0.2867
INT	0.086534	0.035395	2.444819	0.0198
LMC	0.274532	0.410441	0.668871	0.5081
LCPS	0.855158	0.466675	2.832449	0.0057
ECM(-1)	-0.025261	0.163061	-0.154920	0.8778

Source: Author's computation using e-view version 10

R –Square	0.929783
Adjusted R-squared	0.921522
F-Statistics	112.5529
Durbin-Watson stat	2.121715
Prob (F-statistics)	0.000000

4.5 Interpretation of the Regression Result

The value of the R-square and the adjusted R-square in table 4.3 show that the explanatory variables are robust in explaining variation in the dependent variables (LDI), given their values as 0.929783 and 0.921522 respectively.

The F-statistics measures the overall significance of the explanatory parameter. From the result report in table 4.3 above, our computed value of f-statistics is 112.5529, while its probability is 0.0000, given this value we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which state that there is a significant relationship between the variance of estimated regression model.

A' priori criteria is used to determine the existing economic theories which indicate the sign of the economic parameter under consideration. From the estimated regression model it was obtained from the coefficient Column that all the variables conform to a' priori expectation ranging from market capitalization and credit to private sector both have positive sign as expected, meanwhile, interest have negative sign as expected. This further suggests that increase in any of former variables increase the real gross domestic product while an decrease in interest rate would lead to an increase in real gross domestic product, all at a given percentage respectively.

T-statistics, this is the measure used to determine the individual statistical significance of the variables in the model. From the model it was obtained that the interest rate and credit to private sector in Nigeria were statistically significant at 5%, market capitalization were statistically insignificant, however, this implies that the financial liberalization contribute significantly to real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

The Durbin-Watson statistics is used to test for the presence or otherwise of autocorrelation in our model. When the value of Durbin-Watson is closer or a little bit above 2, it means the absence of autocorrelation amongst the explanatory parameter (Koutsoyannis 1997) from the table 4.3 above, it was obtained that our Durbin-Watson result is (2), this satisfy the above stated condition. This further means the absence of autocorrelation among the explanatory variables.

The error correction model term ECM (-1) of about -0.025% is significant with the expected negative sign. The right sign indicates strong feedback effect of deviation of real gross domestic product from its long-run growth path. The coefficient of the error term is -0.025261 this shows that about 25% of the discrepancies between the actual and the equilibrium value of the real gross domestic product is corrected in each period (annually)

4.6 Hypothesis Testing

The researcher in this study formulated hypotheses and this has to be verifying in order to find out the validity of otherwise of such proposition. The research hypothesis is based on relevant statistics from the regression result. We use the null hypothesis for this analysis

Hypothesis One

Ho: Interest rate does not have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy

From the regression result we discovered that in the t-statistics interest rate is -2.44819 while its probability is 0.0198. Since its probability is less than 0.05 desired level of significance we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, we therefore conclude in favor of alternative hypothesis which states that interest rate have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy

Hypothesis Two

Ho: market capitalization does not have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy

From the regression result we discovered that in the t-statistics market capitalization is 0.668871 while its probability is 0.5081 Since its probability is greater than 0.05 desired level of significance, we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis, we therefore conclude in favour of null hypothesis which states that market capitalization does not have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy

Hypothesis Three

Ho: Credit to private sector does not have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy

From the regression result we discovered that in the t-statistics Credit to private sector is 2.832449 is while its probability is 0.0057 Since its probability is less than 0.05 desired level of significance, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis, which states that Credit to private sector have significant effect on stability of Nigeria economy

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

This study, used the OLS regression analysis, unit root test, co-integration test and error correction model to examines the nature of the relationship between financial liberalization and domestic investment in Nigeria from 1985-2024. The regression analysis reveals that financial liberalization, proxied by interest rate and credit to private sector has a statistically significant positive effect on domestic investment in Nigeria. That is, the more liberalized the financial the more domestic investment. Unit root test conducted on the individual variables show that all the included variables were stationary at 1st and 2nd differences. Co-integration test conducted shows that there was a long-run equilibrium relationship between the dependent and independent variables in the model. The study concludes that financial liberalization has a positive significant effect on domestic investment in Nigeria. Moreover the study recommends that interest rate should reduce to the barest minimum to enable the private sector to borrow and expand their business. Credit to private sector should be given with low collateral to private sector and follow up should be made to ensure judiciously use of the fund.

5.2 Recommendations

From the findings the following recommendation are made;

1. The Central Bank of Nigeria should implement policies towards the reduction of interest rate in

the country, in that it has a negative relationship with economic growth. Since, as interest rate increases economic growth decreases, interest rate should be controlled to its minimum.

2. The Government of Nigeria should develop policies which are geared toward the supply of more money into the economy, in that result has shown that more money in the economy increases the growth of the economy. This can be done through embarking on capital projects, provision of social infrastructural facilities and so on.
3. Private sector credit should be granted to businesses and organizations by commercial banks. Credit is considered as a key to economic growth especially in developing countries as it lubricates the economy and findings from the study also reveals its positive significant effect on economic growth.

REFERENCES

- Adesegun, O. (2014), Effects of Financial Sector Liberalization on Bank Performance in Nigeria. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 2(1), 59-78. Www.Ea-Journals.Org.
- Agbaeze, E.K. & Onwuka, I.O. (2014). Financial Liberalization and Investments in Nigeria. *Journal Of Research in Economics and International Finance*, 3(1), 12-24.
- Agu, C.C, Orji, A., Eigbiremolen, G. (2014). Financial Liberalization, Interest Rate Structure and Savings Mobilization: The Nigerian Experience. *International Journal of Current Research*, 6(2), 5101-5109.
- Akinsola, Foluso A.; Odhiambo, Nicholas M. (2017): The Impact of Financial Liberalization on Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 5(1),1-11.
- Chinonso E.O. Uzoamaka G.C& Akujuobi, P. A. (2023). financial liberalisation and economic growth nexus: an empirical evidence of Nigeria [1970 – 2020]. *Journal of Advance Research in Business, Management and Accounting (ISSN: 2456-3544)*, 9(2), 1-12.
- Egbetunde, T., Ayinde, T. O. & Balogun, A.A. (2017). Interest Rate Liberalization, Financial Development and Economic Growth in Sub-Saharan African Economies. *African Journal of Economic Review*, Volume V, Issue II, 109-129.
- Fasanya, I.O. & Olayemi, I.A. (2020): Modeling Financial Openness Growth Nexus in Nigeria: Evidence from Bounds Testing to Cointegration Approach, *Future Business Journal*, ISSN 2314-7210, Springer, Heidelberg, 6(1). 1-11,
- Folarin, O.E. (2019). Financial reforms and industrialization: evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Social and Economic Development*, 21(1), 166-189.
- Ngangah, C.O. Egungwu, I & Nduka, A.J (2025). The impact of financial liberalization on economic development In Nigeria: A focus on the human development index (HDI). *Journal of Business and Management*. 5 (5) 38-50
- Nwakwe, C.P, Echekeba, F.N and Ezu, G.K (2025) Department of Banking and Finance, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. *African Banking and Finance Review Journal*, 9 (3) 45-78
- Oji, G.U (2025) Financial deepening and economic growth: A disaggregated effect from Nigeria. *World journal of entrepreneurial development studies*. 10 (2)
- Ozuzu, C., Reginald, S, Nwankwo, N.U. & Odungweru K., N.(2024). Financial Sector Liberalization and Nigeria Economic Growth: A Time-variant Study. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Management*, 9 (6)56-78